

The Decline in Moral Behavior in Students and What is The Role of Educators

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the causes of the factors that influence the decline in morality among Indonesian students. And what efforts should be made to improve morality in students. And what is the role of educators? in that case. In studies This, As for method writing in article This, that is method literature by collecting various reading sources from articles and journals which are then analyzed and then connecting them to the problems discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Morals are an aspect Which very important in life social Which can also be obtained through the educational process. but nowadays there are many cases or actions that deviate from moral values that end on decline moral. Many rules moral Which often violated Because considered ancient And left behind era, especially in the eyes of today's young people and among students. Morals themselves are standards of good and bad for individuals Which in inside there is values morals, social, And culture as a social member. Several reasons caused the decline behavior moral on students, namely, families who lack supervision, influence from social friends, advances in science and technology, and the development of foreign or western culture.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

According to Suseno in (Ananda 2017), moral values are a measure of attitude And behavior somebody, who knows That be measured from attitude Good or bad And right or wrong. Morals are a very important aspect in life social Which Also can be obtained through the educational process. According to Suseno in (Ananda 2017).

IMPLEMENTATION AND METHODS

The research method used in this writing is to use the literature method, namely by collecting various reading materials from various existing sources which are then analyzed and connecting them to the problems discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to Suseno in (Ananda 2017), moral values are a measure of attitude And behavior somebody, who knows That be measured from attitude Good or bad And right or wrong. People will be said to be moral if they behave positively ethics Which Good And No violate norm Which applies in public. Behave Of course it cannot be arbitrary and haphazard, there must be a measure in every attitude we carry out because basically morals are said to be a person's benchmark in behaving in society (Subiyakto Mutiani 2019).

Factors reason The decline Mark Moral on Indonesian students. Following is causal factors decline Moral values to students

1. Weak attitude value person old
2. Technological progress
3. Of faith fades
4. Environmental influences
5. Loss of honesty
6. Loss of sense of responsibility
7. No think Far forward _
8. Low discipline
9. Cognitive factors
10. Emotional factor
11. Personality factors
12. Situational factors
13. Lack of supervision

14. Moral education

15. Family problematic

From these factors, it can be concluded that the decline in morality in students is caused by various complex factors, such as environmental influences, lack of moral education, and internal factors in students. Therefore, holistic and integrated efforts are needed from various parties, such as families, schools and communities, to form good moral behavior in students.

Efforts to increase morale in students

1. Aspects of Parental Education

Parents play an important role in educating and directing children to instill character education which must continue to be done by giving children an understanding of moral values that are in accordance with national culture such as religious nature, honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, love of the country, care about the environment, social and responsibility.

2. Religious Values

In this case, it requires cooperation from all parties, including parents, educators, government and all elements of society, to be equally committed to cultivating national morals based on Pancasila so as to create harmony in life and a religious environment in accordance with the national character.

3. Habituation

Unique and positive habits in the family, school environment and community need to be developed consistently sustainable. Habits leads on formation child morals. For example, giving punishment to children/students who do it mistakes as proof of responsibility for behavior that harms oneself or others.

4. Educational Aspect (School)

Schools are a great medium and means of education important after role educate parent. School becomes a place to expand outlook And knowledge in life social, for this reason the role of educators is very important in providing students with an understanding of the importance of making good use of science and technology.

How role educator in overcoming decline moral behaviorIn environment school authority, personality And exemplary Which owned by The teacher will have a positive impact on the personality and morality of students, from the process of training and habituation or moral development by providing good role models. good, cult, sanctions and a firm attitude from a teacher. Good moral development is not based on teachings that are commands or prohibitions. just. Will but it must be based on providing a good example from a teacher in the school environment. Therefore, the role and responsibility of teachers in improving student morality is:

- 1) Teachers who have the capacity as educators will make themselves role models, role models and identification for students and their environment. Thus, there are certain standards of personal qualities that teachers must have, which include authority, discipline, independence

and responsibility. Regarding responsibility, teachers must: know, as well as understand mark, norm moral, And social, as well as try to behave and act in accordance with these values and norms.

- 2) The role of the teacher as a model and role model is that the teacher is a model or role model for students and everyone else consider he like Teacher. As example, Of course Personally and what the teacher does will get the attention of students and people around him who consider or recognize him as a teacher.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Morals are a very important aspect in life social Which Also can be obtained through the educational process. According to Suseno in (Ananda 2017), moral values are a measure of a person's attitudes and behavior, either That be measured from attitude good or bad, right or wrong. People will be said to be moral if they behave have good ethics and do not violate the norms applicable in society.

The decline in moral values is caused by many factors, both internal and external. To improve morale, the most important aspect is the role of the family, namely parents, apart from that, educators also have a very important role in improving morale morality in students in the educational environment.

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